

Rover for Monitoring Nuclear Reactor Site

Rover Bagi Pemantauan Kawasan Reaktor Nuklear

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ABSTRACT

A nuclear reactor is a place that initiate and control a sustained nuclear chain reaction. In this nuclear reactor site, it emits a variety types of radiation. A radiation that can cause many deadly illness such as cancer mostly. The worker in the reactor site are exposed themselves to these radiations. However, it can be kept to minimal if there is a device to assist them in monitoring the reactor site. This project is to develop a nuclear reactor site monitoring system using a portable rover by using Internet of Things (IoT). Nowadays, the monitoring system like closed-circuit television, known as CCTV can make the monitoring become limited as it is stick-on-wall type. There would be a blind spot for a wide and large area where the CCTV cannot reach to monitor. The wide and large area need a lot of CCTV and sensors to cover the wide range for monitoring purposes. The project consist of camera, sensors, microcontroller, rover and also Android apps. The camera used is pi-camera while sensors used are temperature & humidity sensor (DHT-22) and ultrasonic sensor (HC-SR04). DHT-22 sensor will detect and inform the user about the changes that occur in temperature and humidity of the surroundings while HC-SR04 used to alert the distance of rover from hitting any obstacles. It will then warning the user if there is an upcoming obstacle. All of this is done through the Android apps where the user will get notified, rover controls and also monitor.

Keywords: Monitoring; Internet of Things; Portable rover; Android; Sensors;

ABSTRAK

Reaktor nuklear adalah tempat di mana menjana dan mengawal rantaian reaktor nuklear yang berterusan. Di dalam tapak reaktor nuklear ini, ia memancarkan pelbagai jenis radiasi. Radiasi yang boleh menyebabkan pelbagai penyakit yang membawa maut seperti kanser kebanyakannya. Pekerja di tapak reaktor terdedah diri mereka kepada radiasi ini. Akan tetapi, masalah ini boleh dikurangkan ke tahap minimum jika terdapat peranti untuk membantu mereka dalam pemantauan tapak reaktor tersebut. Projek ini adalah untuk membangunkan sistem pemantauan tapak reaktor nuklear menggunakan rover mudah alih oleh Internet of Things (IoT). Pada masa kini, sistem pemantauan seperti kamera litar tertutup, dikenali sebagai CCTV membuatkan pemantauan menghadapi limitasi dek kerana jenis CCTV tersebut dilekatkan di dinding. Akan terdapat titik hitam untuk kawasan yang luas dan besar di mana pandangan CCTV tidak dapat untuk dicapai bagi tujuan pemantauan. Projek ini terdiri daripada kamera, alat-alat pengesan, mikropengawal, rover dan juga aplikasi Android. Kamera yang digunakan adalah pi-camera manakala alat-alat pengesan yang digunakan adalah pengesan suhu & kelembapan (DHT-22) dan pengesan ultrasonik (HC-SR04). Pengesan DHT-22 akan mengesan dan maklumkan kepada pengguna tentang perubahan yang berlaku berkaitan suhu dan juga kelembapan di kawasan sekeliling sementara HC-SR04 digunakan untuk peka bagi jarak rover daripada melanggar sebarang halangan. Ianya kemudian memberi amaran kepada pengguna jika terdapat halangan yang mendatang. Kesemua ini dikawal melalui aplikasi Android di mana pengguna akan mendapat notifikasi, pengawalan rover dan juga pemantauan.

Kata kunci: Pemantauan; Internet of Things; Rover mudah alih; Android; Pengesan;

INTRODUCTION

In this era, security and monitoring plays a major important role. An effective security and monitoring system can give an early warning in case there is an emergency or occurrence of undesired event occurs. However, if the monitoring system can move in the monitoring area, the wider area of monitoring can be done with an optimum equipment. Security and

monitoring for nuclear site is very important. This is because we do not want the equipment and tools inside the nuclear reactor falls to the hand of irresponsible person. Advance yet effective security system and monitoring need to be used to overcome the problem from happening. This nuclear materials can make as destroyer material if fall on to irresponsible hand. Effective monitoring system is also required to detect radiation leakage. Radiation

that come out of the nuclear materials can cause cells in our body is exposed to cancer. Based on common type, exposure towards radiation increase risk of cancer. Usually, contributor to the risk including with a background of natural radiation, medical procedure, occupation exposure, nuclear accident and others.

Most closed-circuit television system or also known as CCTV, in our time, limit its observation. This is due to the CCTV system is attached on the wall. Thus, make its supervision be limited to one area only. Observation is one of the big factor in securities. Effective and thorough observation, can prevent undesired situation from happening. Observation that is efficient and effective enable us to control the area easily. It indirectly can tighten the security in the area. CCTV that attached on the wall make the supervision be limited. We need large amount of CCTV to cover a wide and large area, which increases the investment cost. The used of money for installation, purchase and CCTV maintenance also needs to be counted.

In this study, a smart rover monitoring system is proposed to move the CCTV, to eliminate the limited monitoring range of traditional wall-mounted CCTV making the monitoring system more efficient. The cost of installation, purchase and maintenance significantly decrease storage usage and save investment costs (Abaya et al. 2014). On the rover, there would be sensors, microcontroller and also CCTV. This rover is controllable by the

user. The user is able to monitor the nuclear reactor site live wherever they wanted to. It can be moved in all direction. With the help of Internet of Things, all of this is possible to do.

The security and monitoring system is more interesting and more easy to use when it can be used anywhere. With the introduction of Internet of Things also known as IoT, this system can help the user interactive much more effective, easy and user friendly. As an example, if a moving object is detected, the system will send a signal in siren sound or send an email to show any fire or intruder (Abaya et al. 2014).The user also can access to the system wherever they want as long as the user has Internet connection. This IoT technology is not only ease us but also can save our time. This is due to we do not need to trouble ourselves to go to the site just to look at the CCTV. In fact, the user can monitors directly from the provided Android apps. This would make the user much more ease and can make an early action if needed.

METHODOLOGY

In this section detail the role of each component used and steps taken in project development. The components used in this project are Raspberry Pi, pi-camera, motorized rover, temperature & humidity sensor, ultrasonic detector and Android apps. FIGURE 1 shows the flow chart of temperature & humidity sensor to the user. Meanwhile, FIGURE 2 shows the overall components that used in this project.

FIGURE 1. Flowchart of temperature and humidity sensor (DHT-22)

FIGURE 2. The overall components and systems of the project.

Raspberry Pi 3B

Raspberry Pi is a microcontroller used to control sensors, camera and also motors. Raspberry Pi also used due to its ability which provide distinctive Wi-Fi module. This card can be controlled with Android application through Internet network. Model used in this project is Raspberry Pi 3B, that is among of the latest model in the market.

Raspberry Pi is an operating system free based on Debian that optimize for Raspberry Pi's hardware. Raspberry Pi card for receipt of commands sent be the user and according to the order nature (Lamine & Abid 2014). An operating system for program set basis and utility which made the Raspberry Pi functions. It is a platform where the coding for sensors, application also motor included to be handled by Raspberry Pi's microcontroller.

Pi camera

Pi camera used in this project for monitoring purposes. The user can monitor the place whenever they want. This pi camera is attach to the Raspberry Pi and coded to activate its function for monitoring. Normally, device automatically tell consumers by an SMS together with image, with that increase the security level (Vigneswari et al. 2015).

Pi camera will be connected to Raspberry Pi 3B. The camera cable will be attached in its special connector between Ethernet port and HDMI port, with silver connector facing HDMI. This pi camera enable the user to monitor live stream through the Android apps.

Motorize rover

Motorize rover that spur on 4-by-4 is used in this project. This rover is suitable because it could accommodate sensors and camera above it. Motor driver is used to control all four motor that got the command from the Raspberry Pi. Among Raspberry Pi and the motor, the speed is control by the PWM command. This motorize rover is the platform where the microcontroller and sensors will be place above it.

This motorize rover will be functioned to move the rover in 6 different directions. Rover can travel multidirectional to move about in tight spaces (Martin 2012).It is controlled by PWM that give the different speed of rotation between the motor in order to move the rover in specific direction. If the rover wish to turn left, thus the motor in the right side is slightly faster than the left while if the rover wish to turn right, the motor on the left side is slightly faster than the right side. As when the rover wish to reverse to the left, the right side motor will be reverse slightly faster than the left side and it is vice versa for reverse to the right. FIGURE 3 shows the direction available for the rover to turn.

FIGURE 3. The direction available for the rover to move and turn.

Ultrasonic Sensor

Ultrasonic sensor used to prevent the rover from violate any obstacle or object. It will be controlled and monitored by Raspberry Pi. Optimum distance will be fixed to it. If the distance between any object/obstacle and rover draws near, a warning signal will be given to the user who is steering the rover, telling that there is an object/obstacle upcoming. If the object is too close and passed the fixed threshold level, Raspberry Pi will immediately alert the user to stop the rover from hitting the object/obstacle. The object avoidance algorithm is concerned (Ruan & Li 2014). By using the formula,

$$distance = \frac{\left(\frac{period}{2}\right)}{29.1}$$

The ultrasonic sensor changes the signal to the measured distance in centimeter.

The ultrasonic sensor will be put at the backside and front side of the rover. This is due to avoid the rover from hitting any object/obstacle in the front when moving forward and also at the back when reversing. The sensor is connected into the GPIO slot of Raspberry Pi.

Temperature & Humidity Sensor

For the temperature & humidity sensor, the type used is DHT-22. It is connected to the GPIO port of Raspberry Pi. Adafruit DHT is needed to be import in the coding to make it functioning. After that, the read code is apply and the display of temperature and humidity is appear.

The DHT-22 would detect any changes in temperature and humidity, sensing the ambient

temperature and humidity prevailing (Agaskar et al. 2016). It would then be updated to the user interface of Android apps. Thus the user can take any initial act if the changes consider as a danger.

Android Apps

Android Studio is sued as a platform for Android apps. With the use of this application, the user can control the rover and also receive the signal from the microcontroller through the Internet.

In the Android apps that has been upload to the smartphone, there are buttons for steering the rover to move in the given direction. The apps needs to be connected to Internet network so that it can communicate with the microcontroller of Raspberry Pi. User needs to connect by Wi-Fi that have the same network where Raspberry Pi connected to join Internet through subnet that same used by Raspberry Pi (Hossain et al. 2016). A display of temperature and humidity by DHT-22 sensor are provided in the apps. With this displays, the user can monitor the temperature and humidity changes in the area. Thus, the user can monitor on live whenever they want through this apps.

RESULT

In this section, the result of the sensors, motor and also pi camera is shown.

Ultrasonic Sensor (HC-SR04)

The ultrasonic sensor is measured between the distance and the ultrasonic reading. The result is then filled in the TABLE 1 below.

TABLE 1. The table of ultrasonic sensor for front side and back side.

HC-SR04 (Front side)	
Distance (cm)	Ultrasonic Pulse Reading
3.0	0.000174999
6.0	0.000349045
9.0	0.000525951
12.0	0.000701189
15.0	0.000876188

HC-SR04 (Back side)	
Distance (cm)	Ultrasonic Pulse Reading
3.0	0.000174999
6.0	0.000352286
9.0	0.000523090
12.0	0.000699043
15.0	0.000872850

The ultrasonic reading is taken as a raw reading. It is straightly from the ultrasonic sensor itself. From the table above, the graph of distance in

centimeter against ultrasonic reading is plotted as shown in FIGURE 4 below.

FIGURE 4. The graph of best line of ultrasonic sensor for front side and back side of the rover.

As shown in FIGURE 4, the graph of best line is obtained. As from it, the equation of ultrasonic sensor for front side and back side are calculated from it. With this equation, the measured distance between the ultrasonic sensor and the object can be obtained.

Temperature & Humidity Sensor

The next experiment that was conducted is to test the sensitivity and reliability of the temperature and

humidity sensor. The temperature and humidity reading is measured between 7.00 a.m. until 5.00 p.m. on a normal weather. The result obtain is as in TABLE 2 below and the corresponding graph is plotted in FIGURE 5. Based on this graph, it shows that the sensor properly captured the level of humidity of a typical Malaysian weather whereby, the environment is less humid around the midday and more humid when the temperature decreases. This shows the reliability of the sensor selected in this project.

TABLE 2. The result obtain from temperature & humidity sensor.

Time	Temperature (°C)	Humidity (%)
0700	25.7	80.5
0900	28.5	77.6
1100	31.5	71.2
1300	32.0	68.3
1500	31.4	70.4
1700	30.3	74.8

FIGURE 5. Graph of temperature and humidity sensor from 0700 hour until 1700 hour.

Motorize Rover

The speed of the motorized rover is controls by the value of its PWM through the motor driver named L298N. The experiment that was conducted is to determine the time taken for the rover to reach a

specified distance in a straight line to capture its corresponding speed base on PWM value, and the result is as shown in TABLE 3. The speed is based on the average of the three experiment using 3 different distances is plotted in FIGURE 6.

TABLE 3. Speed for the rover to move in a straight line in specific distance.

PWM (%)	Time (s)			Speed (cm/s)
	10 cm distance	20 cm distance	30 cm distance	
20	1.71	3.03	4.11	6.58
40	0.74	1.11	1.51	17.13
60	0.48	0.8	1.13	24.13
80	0.44	0.72	0.98	27.04
100	0.31	0.57	0.75	35.78

FIGURE 6. Graph of speed for the rover to move in a straight line.

The interface for the user in Android apps is developed by using Android Studio. The result are as shown in FIGURE 7 and FIGURE 8.

FIGURE 7. The login page of Android apps

FIGURE 8. Android Apps to control and monitoring the rover.

DISCUSSIONS

The Raspberry Pi 3 Model B is surprisingly can connect the Internet in a long distance. This microcontroller is very suitable to be used in this project. The pi camera managed to provide a satisfaction quality of resolution for the user to monitor the site. The shield is needed to cover up the rover to make sure that the component on it does not get damaged by radiation emits from the nuclear reactor. The formula for ultrasonic sensor is proved and can be used, the graph of best line shows that the distance is perpendicular to the ultrasonic pulse reading. The temperature and humidity sensor are in a good condition. Radiation sensor is very useful for the project for future work. Gas can interspersed with an inert gas like halogen gas to make tube operate in voltage that is lower (Haider A. Khalaf 2012). The Android Apps for the user interface managed to be done on time. However, the interaction between the Raspberry Pi and the Android apps is not completed. It may be done for future work for the upgrade.

CONCLUSION

As a conclusion, the project to develop the portable rover for nuclear monitoring system has been successfully developed. The interface of Android apps is completed. The future work for this project is to complete the connection between the Android apps and Raspberry Pi to make it fully function by the user. Moreover, the use of sensor to detect radiation (Geiger counter) is also one of the future work.

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